

 [VIDEO: How to use this page](#)

 Create snapshot of instruments

Last snapshot: 2023-08-18 14:34

This page allows you to build and customize your data collection instruments one field at a time. You may add new fields or edit existing ones. New fields may be added by clicking the **Add Field** buttons. You can begin editing an existing field by clicking on the **Delete** icon. To reorder the fields, simply **drag and drop** a field to a different position within the form below. NOTE: While in development status, all field changes will take effect immediately in real time.

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Current instrument: **IMPRECISION + TSA description (repeatable)**

[Preview instrument](#)

[Add Field](#) [Add Matrix of Fields](#) [Import from Field Bank](#)

 Variable: instrument4

Instrument 4 contents

- **TSA - Outcome details**
- **TSA - Methods**
 - **Dichotomous/continuous**
- **TSA - Graphical presentation and results**
 - **Graphics**
 - **Results**

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Variable: tsaout_tsas

Contains embedded fields

What is the outcome to which TSA was applied (pick only one!)

Primary	{tsaout_prim_tsa_1} {tsaout_prim_tsa_2} {tsaout_prim_tsa_3} {tsaout_prim_tsa_4}{tsaout_prim_tsa_5}{tsaout_prim_tsa_6} {tsaout_prim_tsa_7}{tsaout_prim_tsa_8}{tsaout_prim_tsa_9} {tsaout_prim_tsa_10}{tsaout_prim_tsa_11}{tsaout_prim_tsa_12} {tsaout_prim_tsa_13}{tsaout_prim_tsa_14}{tsaout_prim_tsa_15} {tsaout_prim_tsa_16}{tsaout_prim_tsa_17}{tsaout_prim_tsa_18} {tsaout_prim_tsa_19}{tsaout_prim_tsa_20}
Secondary	{tsaout_sec_tsa_1}{tsaout_sec_tsa_2}{tsaout_sec_tsa_3}{tsaout_sec_tsa_4} {tsaout_sec_tsa_5}{tsaout_sec_tsa_6} {tsaout_sec_tsa_7}{tsaout_sec_tsa_8}{tsaout_sec_tsa_9}{tsaout_sec_tsa_10} {tsaout_sec_tsa_11}{tsaout_sec_tsa_12}{tsaout_sec_tsa_13} {tsaout_sec_tsa_14}{tsaout_sec_tsa_15}{tsaout_sec_tsa_16} {tsaout_sec_tsa_17}{tsaout_sec_tsa_18}{tsaout_sec_tsa_19} {tsaout_sec_tsa_20}
Exploratory	{tsaout_exp_tsa_1}{tsaout_exp_tsa_2}{tsaout_exp_tsa_3}{tsaout_exp_tsa_4} {tsaout_exp_tsa_5}{tsaout_exp_tsa_6}{tsaout_exp_tsa_7}{tsaout_exp_tsa_8} {tsaout_exp_tsa_9}{tsaout_exp_tsa_10} {tsaout_exp_tsa_11}{tsaout_exp_tsa_12}{tsaout_exp_tsa_13} {tsaout_exp_tsa_14}{tsaout_exp_tsa_15}{tsaout_exp_tsa_16} {tsaout_exp_tsa_17}{tsaout_exp_tsa_18}{tsaout_exp_tsa_19} {tsaout_exp_tsa_20}
Subgroup analyses	{tsaout_sub}
If the outcome to which TSA was applied is not listed above, please describe here:	{tsaout_comment}

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Variable: tsaout_grade *Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn]<>0*

How was the outcome GRADE'd?

- High
- Moderate
- Low
- Very low
- The outcome was not GRADE'd

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Variable: studcon_grade_lim_ben *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedown] = 1*

NEW QUESTION

Were limits for important benefit defined for the outcome in question?

- Yes
- No

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Variable: studcon_grade_lim_harm *Branching logic: [studcon_gradedown] = 1*

NEW QUESTION

Were limits for important harm defined?

- Yes
- No

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Variable: tsaout_grade_imprecision *Branching logic: [tsaout_grade]<>0*

How much was imprecision downgraded?

- NEW OPTION: 0 levels
- 1 level
- 2 levels
- 3 levels
- NEW OPTION: Unclear
- DISCONTINUED - Imprecision was not explicitly downgraded
- DISCONTINUED - Other

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Variable: tsaout_grade_imprecision_txt *Branching logic: [tsaout_grade_imprecision] = 4*

NEW QUESTION

How was it unclear how much imprecision was downgraded?

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Variable: tsaout_grade_imprecision_txt_2 *Branching logic: [studcon_gradeyn] <> 0*

NEW QUESTION

Do you have further comments on the imprecision assessment of the particular outcome?

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Variable: revision_divider_study_desc_2

Everything below this field does not require revision

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Variable: tsaout_header

TSA - Outcome details